

Proximal Humerus Fractures:

Burst fractures

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Introduction

The optimal treatment for proximal humerus fractures remains a topic of debate. Most surgeons agree on non-operative treatment for simple fractures in elderly patients and ORIF (open reduction and internal fixation) for 3- and 4-part fractures in younger patients (1, 2).

Studies such as PROFHER (3) show similar outcomes for operative and non-operative treatments, regardless of fracture pattern or the patient's age.

Materials and Methods

We present a short series of 10 patients identified from a cohort of 142 consecutive patients with severely displaced 4-part fractures, which we term “burst fractures.” Of these 10 patients, 7 were treated operatively and 3 were treated non-operatively. Among the 7 operated patients, 4 underwent ORIF and 3 received reverse shoulder prostheses. Full data for the 142 patients is available through ICUC tags, utilizing a new search tool (4, 5).

We present the analysis of the 3 patients who were treated non-operatively. For most surgeons, the ideal treatment for these 3 patients would have been a reverse shoulder prosthesis. Nevertheless, all three patients did well with non-operative treatment. This study suggests the possibility of a non-operative treatment trial for burst fractures, with reverse prosthesis considered as a rescue surgery if needed.

Fig. 1. The 3 patients non-operatively treated at: <https://icuctags.net/> / Proximal Humerus / Tag “Z-1” + Tag “TREATMENT: Non-operative”

Fig. 2. Burst fracture. 65 years-old female, non-operatively treated. Good final result. ICUC Score FL1=, P0 at 76 weeks. [ICUC ID: 11-VI-321](#) (6)

References

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